

LINGUISTIC AND PHRASEOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE RHETORIC OF THE LAWYER'S SPEECH DURING THE TRIAL

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Аннотация: Ҳиссий бўёқдор лексика, фразеологик ибора таркибидаги сўзларнинг ўзаро бирикиб кетиш даражаси, ибора воқеликни бевосита акс эттиради, ҳуқуқий фразеологик бирликларни келиб чиқиши, халқларнинг умумий ижтимоий-сиёсий яшаш шароитлари.

Калит сўзлар: фразеологик қўшилма, фразеологик бутунлик, фразеологик чатишмалар, юрист риторикаси, тўғри талаффуз этиш, тон, тембр, пауза, этимологик изоҳ.

Аннотация: лексика с эмоциональной окраской, степень взаимосвязанности слов во фразеологизме, фразеологизм непосредственно отражает действительность, происхождение юридических фразеологизмов, общие социально-политические условия жизни народов.

Ключевые слова: фразеологическое сочетание, фразеологическая целостность, фразеологические коллизии, адвокатская риторика, правильное произношение, тон, тембр, пауза, этимологическое объяснение.

Annotation: lexicon with emotional coloring, the degree of interlinking of words in a phraseological phrase, the phrase directly reflects reality, the origin of legal phraseological units, the general socio-political living conditions of nations.

Key words: phraseological combination, phraseological integrity, phraseological conflicts, lawyer's rhetoric, correct pronunciation, tone, timbre, pause, etymological explanation.

The national and cultural characteristics of the lawyer's rhetoric are manifested in its multiple linguo-phraseological aspects compared to other layers of the language. Therefore, in this article, we pay special attention to the phraseology of the lawyer's rhetoric in English and Uzbek languages.

It is well known that the persuasiveness of a speech depends on skillfully supporting it with evidence and facts. Accordingly, we believe that rhetoric is a lawyer's "weapon" on the battlefield, the only means by which he can achieve victory in his legal profession. In other words, a lawyer should structure his speech in such a way that it should be very clear, fluent and understandable. In addition, such a speech must also have the power to influence. Achieving such influence is much easier for a lawyer than for a prosecutor. Because the prosecutor's speech is dominated by formality and firmness, he quotes many laws

in his speech. Accordingly, the prosecutor's speech has few opportunities for impressiveness, emotionally colored lexis is almost never used. The lawyer's speech is much freer compared to the prosecutor's speech, and it is possible to use some emotional words. In this, rhetorical knowledge, skills and skills serve as a basis for a lawyer.

Therefore, it is not just a simple speech at the court session, but also very clear, formal, based on legal facts and legal logical consistency of the speech.

In addition, phonetic elements are also very important in the lawyer's speech. In particular, it is necessary to be able to correctly pronounce speech sounds, use tone, timbre and pause correctly. This is the main factor for the listeners to understand the opinion expressed by the lawyer without any difficulty, to imagine how the lawyer interprets it.

The rich history of the English language, rich English culture, various sources of phraseological units that confirm its connections with other cultures not only enrich the language, but also enliven, develop and enrich it.

The degree of interlinking of words in a phraseological phrase and the relationship between the meaning of the phrase and the specific meanings of the words in it are different. Accordingly, all phraseology in the current Uzbek literary language are divided into three groups in the literature of Uzbek linguistics, i.e. phraseological combination, phraseological whole, phraseological combination. Taking into account the above features of the phrases in legal rhetoric, when they were examined in terms of the type of phrase they belong to, it was observed that they fully correspond to phraseological compounds. It is known that phraseological compounds are built on the figurative meaning of one of the words in the composition, they have the following main signs:

1. Since the overall meaning of the phrase consists of the meaning of its components, the phrase directly reflects reality.
2. Regardless of whether some words in the phrase are used figuratively or not, the phrase as a whole does not have a figurative meaning.
3. The syntactic connection between the components of the phrase is alive (that is, it is known what parts of the sentence it consists of), but constant.
4. Although the phrase is constant, sometimes other words are inserted between the constant words in it.

These signs of phraseological compounds are fully compatible with the above features of expressions characteristic of legal rhetoric. This allows us to conclude that legal rhetorical expressions are mainly composed of phraseological compounds.

In the lexicon of legal rhetoric, there is an objective reason for the non-use of phraseological integrity and phraseological confusion (even if they are used in small quantities). It is known that the words in the phraseological unit and phraseological combination have lost their independence of lexical meaning, almost all parts have acquired a figurative meaning and express a single integrated meaning. As a result, they have strong emotional-expressiveness compared to phraseological compounds. These features of phraseological confusion and phraseological wholes do not correspond to the signs of neutrality, strictness, and formality of legal rhetoric. That is why phraseological unity and phraseological conflict are hardly used in the lexicon of legal rhetoric.

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